

DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATIONS OF GLASS FIBER BARS AS A REINFORCED IN CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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1 GFRP rebar as internal reinforcement concrete

Rapid technological advances in building materials have contributed to the impressive gain advantage in civil engineering in areas such as security, economy and functionality of the structures built to serve the needs of society, improving standard of living of people. Among these materials, one has been in use since the early 40's, but has recently gained the attention of the engineers involved in construction of civil structures: composite material made of fibers embedded in polymeric resin, also known FRPs (fiber reinforced polymer).

Conventional concrete structures are reinforced with nonprestressed and prestressed steel. The steel is initially protected against corrosion by the alkalinity of the concrete, usually resulting in durable and serviceable construction. For many structures subjected to aggressive environments, such as marine structures, bridges, and parking garages exposed to deicing salts, combinations of moisture, temperature, and chlorides reduce the alkalinity of the concrete and result in the corrosion of reinforcing steel. The corrosion process ultimately causes concrete deterioration and loss of serviceability.

Composite materials offer significant benefits if their application is correct, taking into account aspects such as cost and durability. These materials has other advantages such as its high tensile strength and stiffness to weight ratio, its ability to resist corrosion and chemical attack, controllable thermal expansion and damping conditions and higher electromagnetic neutrality compared to other materials.

The use of fiber-reinforced bars polymer (GFRP) to enhance the corrosion behavior of conventional reinforced concrete structures, appears as one of the many techniques presented [1], [2]. In particular, the GFRP bars offer great potential for use as reinforcement in conditions in which reinforced concrete with steel offers unacceptable conditions of service [3], [4]. Therefore, the use of GFRP as armed bars of concrete has been in development since the early 1960's in America and the 1970 in Europe and Japan, although the overall level of research, demonstration and commercialization has increased markedly since the 1980's, using mainly GFRP reinforced concrete in structures that require high resistance to corrosion or electromagnetic absolute transparency.

The bars GFRP are normally manufactured by the pultrusion process or a variant such as "pull-forming." This type of process makes it possible to obtain products with high fiber content, 60% and 80% of its volume, and a homogeneous distribution of fiber in the bar cross section. Typical GFRP reinforcement products are grids, bars, fabrics and rods. The bars have various types of cross-sectional shapes (square, round, solid and hollow) and deformation systems (exterior wound fibers, sand coatings and separately deformations). Rovings have a high tensile strength and high modulus of elasticity, in addition to being the resistive component of the composite. The matrix is the required material used to bind the fibers to obtain a homogenization among them, but also serves to confer protection and dimensional stability of the GFRP bar.

2 Development of GFRP rebar as reinforcement in RC

The mechanical behavior of GFRP reinforcement differs from the behavior of conventional steel reinforcement. The analysis of sections reinforced with GFRP, bending and shear, in many cases is compared to conventional analysis of steel sections, although the significant differences in terms of properties and mechanical behavior, so a change is need in the traditional design philosophy. GFRP composites have a linearly elastic stress-strain relationship until failure, no yield, which means that the systems used to design reinforced concrete with this type of reinforcement must take into account the lack of ductility that has the material, unlike steel reinforced concrete.

Currently, the reinforced concrete with GFRP bars is designed using the principles of Ultimate Limit States, ensuring a sufficient strength (with a design safety factor affecting loading and material strength), determining the failure mode and verify adequate adhesion between the materials. Service Limit States, such as deformation, cracks, resistance to fatigue or long-term loads and relaxation (for prestressed concrete), must also be checked.

2.1 Guidelines, codes and specifications of calculation and design published.

The GFRP bars behavior study as reinforcement of concrete structures has certainly evolved since 1954, when Brandt Goldsworthy spoke of the great potential that had this material in certain applications of construction. From then until the decade of the 70, a small number of studies to analyze the feasibility of using GFRP rods as reinforcement of reinforced concrete had made.

From the 1980's and early 90's, the use of GFRP reinforcement in civil engineering applications executed, activated the development of scientific research and methods test on the bar. The work done in Europe, U.S., Japan and Canada were detailed in collections of documents and reports published. The international interest the use of GFRP reinforcement increased dramatically, which led of course, the increase in the number of publications on the hundreds of studies and trials in this field. [5], [6].

As result of this evolution in the behavior of GFRP reinforcement have been published in recent years various codes or design guidelines, (Table 1). Because of the huge variety of types of FRP reinforcement can be found on the market, these guides or standards define the limits of States must meet the design of reinforced concrete elements, causing a lack of uniformity guidelines in the testing methods for each of the materials.

However, one conclusion that seems to have got in all these years of research is GFRP reinforcement should be not relied on to resist compression. International tested data show the compression modulus of GFRP bars is lower that its tensile modulus. Due to the combined effect of this behavior and the relatively lower modulus of GFRP compared with steel, the maximum contribution of compression FRP reinforcement calculated at crushing of concrete is small. Therefore, these codes should neither consider FRP reinforcement as reinforcement in columns nor other in compression members, nor as compression reinforcement in flexural members. Although all of them indicate that the compressive strength of GFRP rods should not be disregarded, requiring further research in this area. This is the basic point of this work, study the behavior of reinforced concrete with GFRP bar under compression loads.

2.2 RTHp rebar: characterization

After the technical and practical analysis of this material, we get a solution to work both tensile and compression, such as steel, creating ES Patent No. 2,325,011 by RTHp Company [7]. This solution adds to the longitudinal fibers (1), a cross-fiber fabric (2), reinforcing the surface, which brings stability to longitudinal fiber for compression work, Figure 2-a. This is the main contribution of these bars to existing products. This mat/fabric prevents buckling of the fibers because there is no space between them; avoid local buckling [8].

If we analyze compression test until failure of traditional bar and RTHp bar, the first is broke by "explosion" similar to that occurring in a concrete pillar without stirrups, Figure 1, and the second case is broke by buckling as shown in Figure 2.

The research was based on the manufacture and testing of different kind of bars, with different diameter, more 500 specimens were tested, in order to obtain the results certification by "Eduardo Torroja" Institute of Construction Science, CSIC. The bars are made of fiberglass and vinylester resin, with 75% fiber volume, and manufactured by the pultrusion process.

2.3.1. Tensile Test

In the tensile test, according to the UNE-EN ISO 527-1:1996, we get the load and the elongation at break suffered by the specimen. The evaluation and analysis of the results of this test allow us to know the tensile mechanical properties of GFRP bar, such as its strength and its modulus of elasticity.

Following the recommendations of ACI 440.3R-04 and UNE-EN 527-1:1996, the specimens were prepared with their respective diameters and lengths, formed by a central section, object of the test, and two extreme sections, which adequately prepared to allow their attachment to the gags of the press, depending on the diameter of the specimen.

The experimental values for each of the samples ranged from a null value for the effort until the breaking of the specimen. The measurement of the elastic modulus, in the longitudinal direction, was performed using an extensometer between 20% and 50% of the fracture load, value recommended by ACI 440.3R.

2.3.1. Compression Test

In the compression test according to ISO 5893:2002, a specimen is subjected to a compressive load along its longitudinal axis and at constant speed up to its failure, measuring the load and the shortening of by the specimen. The evaluation and analysis of this type of test, allow us to know the mechanical characteristics to compression of GFRP bar, such as its strength and modulus of elasticity.

The specimens were formed of a central section, object of the test, and two extreme sections covered by two steel bushings. The characteristic lengths of the compression tested GFRP bars were the combined result of personal experience in compression tests and the recommendations of the standards codes, although at present there is not legislation or literature that refers to the characterization compression GFRP bars.

To perform the compression test, a set of plates was designed and built for each family of rounds, one of the dishes being articulated on the other to facilitate the implementation of the test. The compression plates are plates of hardened steel, constructed so that the load on the specimen is entirely axial, transmitted through the polished surfaces, whose flatness is parallel in a plane perpendicular to the axis of loading.

In the compression tests, measurement of elastic modulus in the longitudinal direction was performed using an extensometer between 20% and 50% of the fracture load.

2.3.1. Bond Test

The bond properties of the bars as internal reinforcement concrete structures have been obtained using the "pull out" test, taking as reference Annex D of the UNE-EN 10080. The specimens for the "pull out" tests passed through the curing and setting process, respecting the minimum time before performing the test, as determined by UNE-EN 1766:2000 and ACI 440.3R-04.

The "pull out" test consists of applying a tensile load to a GFRP bar, which is embedded in a certain length within a concrete cube, leaving the other end of the bar without any other cargo. The pulling force is increased until failure occurs or until the bond breaks the GFRP bar, obtaining the relationship between the tensile force applied and the produced slide.

Specimens were prepared for three types of rounds, the diameter 8, 16 and 32 mm, when taken as representative of the following groups: fine series (8, 10 and 12 mm), medium series (16 and 20 mm) and thick series (25 and 32 mm), respectively. They also present a surface coating of silica sand to facilitate its adhesion to concrete.

2.3.1. Shear Test

The objective of this test is to determine the shear strength of the bars for use as stirrups, so bars have been tested at 12 mm in diameter, considered the most common size.

The mechanical properties of RTHp bars, depending on the diameter, were obtained in these tests, and after they achieved their certification by CSIC [9]. These values are taken as characteristic mechanical properties for the design and cross-check of

reinforced concrete elements, (Table 2, Table 3, Table 4 and Table 5).

2.3 Design rules

Spanish Structural Concrete Standard, EHE-08, is the current design code for concrete structures with structural safety requirements in Spain, giving sufficient techniques to meet guarantees. This code, in article 2, when the structure can be considered special or unique, it indicates that the rules will apply with the adaptations and additions, under the liability established by the author.

We are in this case; we want to design reinforced concrete structures with GFRP internal reinforcement. For this purpose, we studied EHE-08 code, changing the rules and establishing the necessary adjustments and additional provisions, to obtain solutions, partially or totally different from the procedures laid down in it, but according to the mechanical characteristics that this material has for building these structures, with a valid characterization of RTHp fiberglass bar as described in the previous tables.

Any structure should be designed and built with a level of acceptable safety, so that it is capable of supporting all actions that can be found during the construction period, and life expectancy of the project. Also, it should also be able to withstand the aggressive environment in which it is located.

To ensure the above requirements, the EHE-08 uses the Limit States, analysing the situations that exceed the structure, and needs to ensure durability. Purpose is to verify, for each limit state, the design values are equal or less than to ultimate strength. Therefore the characteristic values are weighted by a partial safety factor, which affect the material strength and value of the loads.

The general design recommendations for concrete elements reinforced with GFRP bars are based on principles of equilibrium and compatibility and the constitutive laws of the materials. Furthermore, the brittle behavior of both FRP reinforcement and concrete allows consideration to be given to either FRP rupture or concrete crushing as the mechanisms that control failure.

Both strength and working stress design approaches were considered by this investigation. The researchers opted for the strength design approach of reinforced concrete members reinforced with GFRP bars to ensure consistency with other documents. These design recommendations are based on limit state design principles in that an FRP-reinforced concrete member is designed based on its required strength and then checked for serviceability criteria, fatigue endurance, creep rupture endurance. FRP-reinforced concrete members have a relatively small stiffness after cracking. Consequently, permissible deflections under service loads can control the design.

Serviceability can be defined as satisfactory performance under service load conditions. The serviceability provisions given in EHE-08 need to be modified for FRP-reinforced members due to differences in properties of steel and FRP, such as lower stiffness, bond strength, and corrosion resistance. The substitution of FRP for steel on an equal-area basis, for example, would typically result in larger deflections and wider crack widths.

The design of GFRP-reinforced concrete members for flexure is analogous to the design of steel-reinforced concrete members. Experimental data on concrete members reinforced with GFRP bars showed that bending capacity can be calculated based on assumptions similar to those made for members reinforced with steel bars, modified them with GFRP characteristic coefficient. The different mechanical properties of GFRP bars, however, affect shear strength and must be considered. The shear capacity were studied and the use of GFRP stirrups.

3 Applications of RTHp rebar as reinforcement in RC

After certification of the values characteristic of the mechanical properties of RTHp round, have been numerous applications of the material in last years. All of them cover specific needs with the characteristics of the material. In this way, has been used as internal reinforcement of the reinforced concrete slab of Granada tram, avoiding producing steel shielding, Figure 7; in the port of Javea

(Alicante) on the foundation of a wall, Figure 8, and beam in the port of Valencia, that is in construction, for its resistance to corrosion, due to its high durability against sea salt.

On the other hand, after the results, is being given new uses for the rods, as reinforced piles. We have been reinforced piles with GFRP rebar to be kneeling. The kneel has been completed with results that confirm the excellent compression behavior of the RTHp rod, opening a new area in this research.

4 References

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Table 1. International codes and guidelines FRP design

Figure 1. Compression test of a traditional GFRP bar

Figure 2. Configuration and compression test of RTHp bar

Figure 7. Granada's tram slab (Spain)

Figure 8. Foundation wall. Javea's port (Spain)

ϕ (mm)	Strength (MPa)		Elastic Modulus (MPa)	
	Nominal	Charact	Nominal	Charact
8	855,8	916,1	38276	36107
10	779,1	745,0	42634	38488
12	637,9	620,5	41125	39573
16	695,5	637,7	42477	40140
20	723,7	700,6	43590	40970
25	722,8	623,5	39929	35453
32	720,1	635,5	39681	33370

Table 2. Tensile properties

ϕ (mm)	Strength (MPa)		Elastic Modulus (MPa)	
	Nominal	Charac	Nominal	Charac
8	463,5	425,5	39934	32713
10	449,5	398,2	46295	38492
12	469,7	418,5	41894	35966
16	449,1	426,7	50804	46302
20	443,6	408,8	44861	40791
25	371,9	351,2	41993	37956
32	319,2	299,8	40766	36590

Table 3. Compression properties

ϕ (mm)	Failure load (kN)	Characteristic Tensile Strength (kN)
12	11,6	10,22

Table 4. Shear properties

ϕ (mm)	Nominal Strength (MPa)	Failure Strength (MPa)
8	9,21	11,94
16	5,53	6,12
25	5,72	6,16

Table 5. Bond properties